

METHODOLOGY OF INTRODUCING FUTURE MUSIC TEACHERS WITH EXAMPLES OF EPIC CREATION

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Abstract: In this article, there are opinions about the scientific-pedagogical basis and conditions of the methodology of introducing music education students to examples of epic creativity.

Key words: Music education, epic performance, folklore music, master-disciple traditions, methodology.

Introduction:

At the end of the 19th century, in the first half of the 20th century, the great successors of the traditions of performing epics, in order to improve the creative skills of each other's talented performers and musicians, musical evenings were organized in the circle of hos. they performed perfectly. The purpose of such classes was to demand from the master's students to achieve creative perfection in performance as well. The study of epics based on the "Teacher-disciple" school was formed in the distant past and continues to this day. Performing arts lessons have traditionally been taught in a mentor-student format. Each student was under the supervision and education of his teacher. Music art and fiction writing, telling stories, correct pronunciation of words, understanding the meaning of poetry and prose, studying musical heritage were always under the supervision of teachers. The student's independent epic singing in front of the people and music lovers was done with the direct permission of the teacher.

The introduction to the study of the performance of epics in the oral tradition in musicology began around 1924, and the ideas of bringing these musical genres to school music activities began many years later. In the spring of 1980, at the seminar of folklore musicologists held in Khiva, many Uzbek musicologists, composers and pedagogues of higher educational institutions of music noted the high educational value of epics and other professional music genres and said that it is necessary to start teaching them at school.

In 1982, a program for studying the foundations of epics was created and published in the music-pedagogy faculties of pedagogical institutes. At the end of the 1980s, epics were included in school music textbooks, albeit in short form. Since then, the practice of studying professional music genres and involving them in school music activities continues. At the same time, a lot of work has been done on the methodology of studying these epic works at school.

Later, experts expressed their opinions about the methods of learning epics in school music classes and created a guide for teachers. The above-mentioned works have been of some help in solving these problems. But now the problem is not completely solved. In our opinion, the biggest problem is the lack of notation sets, textbooks, training manuals,

recordings of the epic performance in the audio version intended for listening, and technical means in all regions of our country¹.

It is known that all wise artisans, talented poets, musicians and scientists who grew up among the common people were recruited into the palace service. The famous musicians and singers who worked in the association of musicians in the palace provided musical services to the residents of villages and towns until they came into the public eye, and their creative principles were formed on the basis of this simple folk music. Therefore, our great ancestors used bright examples of folk music when creating epics. With the honor of independence, among all our national values, it is envisaged to restore epics, to study their theoretical foundations and practical implementation on a large scale. Approaching from this point of view, we observe that epic performance methods are included in the educational process of general secondary schools by listening to fragments recorded in the performance process, singing some examples.

The system of learning and teaching epics has not yet been fully formed. If we want to look at the past system of this process, we will see the tradition of master discipleship and the oral implementation of this tradition. Nowadays, it is evident that this process is partially based on the European notation system. Both of these methods of learning and mastering have their own advantages and disadvantages. While in the past, the teachers selected young people who were favorable to them, i.e., with strong musical memory, voice and interest, and taught them how to perform epics, nowadays, young people with some average musical abilities are also taught epic music. are engaged in.

This is due to notation and audio recordings of epic performances. In order to master and master such complex and perfect musical genres as epics, it is necessary to learn from experienced teachers and to use notation and audio recordings of different performers as a joint tool². Young people who are studying epics, different methods for learning epics (listening to the performances of mature teachers, teaching them to perform, using improved notation as much as possible, recording their performance on audio tape, listening back, and so on. improve its performance by way of and other) are used. In the process of teaching epic works to students in general secondary education, attention is mainly focused on getting theoretical information about epics and mastering some bright examples of epics or excerpts from them by singing. The reason for this is that students educated in the general secondary education system are expected to be aware of the general nature and characteristics of epics and receive spiritual nourishment from them.

We think that it is necessary and useful to use the following methods in teaching Doston students:

- get acquainted with the theoretical information and practical performance characteristics of epics and other genres of professional music (classical tunes and chants);
- to compare and analyze mature bakhshis who performed epics and their ways of performance;
- in particular, to learn to distinguish between the seriality and structural features of epics during performance;

¹Current issues of teaching the art of status/Iroda Nazarova Molodoy ucheniy.- 2020.-№4(294).

²Matyokubov B. Gilded pages of performance of Khorazm epic.-Khorazm, 1999.-51 p.

- to study the notation of the epics and to find the subtle points of the performance that could not be reflected in the score, and to ensure their status in live performance;
- listening to epic samples in audio and video recordings;
- to regularly study some works from epic and other professional music genres based on the methods mentioned above and strive to improve one's performance;
- performing live performances at some events and concerts³.

When teaching planned songs, the teacher focuses more on song content and authors, musical trends, musical life news, singing in high pitches, longer vocal-choir exercises, smoother, mainly in the middle register. It is recommended to switch to singing in sounds. During this period, it would be appropriate to give students concise and interesting life information about epics, classical melodies and songs, their performance traditions, bright and famous epic performers, and organize conversations. Trying to hear more music. Experiments show that readers often like more colorful epics with exciting adventures. In such works, heroism and other human qualities have a great effect on the students in the harmony of words and music and captivate them. The teacher's professional level, speech, and emotional feelings also play an important role in this. The importance of the interesting and effective course of lessons, the effective use of visual aids, technical tools, and the use of communication factors between disciplines is incomparable. Therefore, a new modern program has been introduced in general secondary schools. First of all, the new program will help to understand the essence of the specific topics of the lesson - epics, epic melodies and other genres of music that belong to the professional music genres of the oral tradition, based on a comparative study with examples of European music.

As in the days of the old system, each type of activity serves its own short purpose and does not have specific minutes (lesson time) for their implementation, listening to music, exercises and listening to songs, exercises and singing songs, and music literacy training. Lessons are not considered an independent part of the lesson, but a musical activity that reveals the content and theme of the lesson. This factor makes it possible to master classical tunes and songs mainly by listening. The subject of the lesson uses new music activities such as interesting rhythmic movements, clapping and children's toy musical instruments, accompaniment to music using rattles, hoops, spoons and other rhythmic instruments, and music creation, which will introduce students to the genres of epics. helps them to master. Due to the presence of active participation and performance features at the heart of these activities, they arouse great interest in students. All types of activities used in the classes are valid as an integral part of the subject of the lesson. In this regard, the subject "Music" belongs to the type of mixed lesson, and the following musical activities, subordinate to the general theme of the lesson, are logically connected:

- music perception (listening) singing:
- musical literacy:
- rhythmic movements and others.

³ Karimov S. Foundations of moral culture (explanatory dictionary of terms used in spiritual and educational work). -T: Science, 1998.

One of the important tasks of the music culture lesson is to develop students' musical abilities. Music perception (listening) and music literacy activities lead to the practice of all other activities with an integral connection. Students' natural musical instruments are their voices. Adapted parts of some epic pieces given in the program for singing are necessary for mastering the style of national musical traditions, forming a bright intonation characteristic of musical heritage, a sense of method (rhythm), and developing students' musical learning ability and epic performance skills.

The methods used during the lesson are oriented to convey the topic to students and are based on evidence from various sources, which makes the organization of lessons more effective in interdisciplinary connection. We will dwell in more detail on a number of methods included in the sentence of such methods

1. Storytelling method. This method is a statement based on vivid, emotional, bright life events and clear educational evidence, literary and artistic scenes about the epic work of a music teacher, and the purpose of its application is to teach students about the musical work, its genre, its performance style and aspects of traditionality, It is intended to introduce in-depth and complete information about the artistic-ideological content, in what situation, by whom and in what order, about skilled performers and authors. Using the story method, the teacher can provide important information about the development and historical roots of Uzbek music culture, relying on rich historical materials.

2. The interview method is one of the most effective methods of didactics. This process consists of a dialogue between the teacher and students. According to the topic of the musical piece, together with the educational material given in the textbook, it is related to other subjects (for example, nature, animal world, literature, history, ecology, mother tongue, etc.), giving examples, asking students questions, describing the works, analyzing their conceptual artistic content, theoretical structure, genre features, using visual aids, students are created comfortable conditions for independent thinking.

3. Explanation method. It is mainly used to provide theoretical information. In imparting knowledge of music literacy, physics (sound and physical properties of sound, sound power, timbre, sound amplitude, etc.) mathematical measurements, note extensions, etc. . It is known from history that music was studied as a component of mathematics until it was recognized as a separate science.

4. Visual teaching methods. It is known that music consists of a moving melody and a system of harmonized sounds. It can only be perceived by listening through the auditory system. It is important to use the knowledge of painting and drawing to write musical notes beautifully (according to the rules of good writing and etiquette).

5. Practical teaching methods are used by the teacher mainly in the process of forming students' qualifications and skills related to practical performance. In this case, the teacher's "personal example", i.e., showing every practical action, is of great importance. Work on vocal-choir skills (sound generation, sound transmission, masked singing, breathing, breathing, pitch, ensemble, diction, intonation), step to music and perform movements (game, dance, gymnastic elements), activities such as accompanying children's musical instruments are carried out using practical methods.

6. Game method - mostly used in elementary classes and gives good results. The musical pieces included in the educational repertoire consist of examples performed by young, psychological characters of children with fun, dance, play-dance movements, and play,

dance and its elements are widely used in their performance. It is given. It is important for the teacher to be aware of the art of dance and its simplest movement elements. As we know, Uzbek folk music folklore, in particular children's folklore songs, are performed by playing a game or through exercises and actions in the nature of a game, and this requires the music teacher to refer to folklore sources when working with such works. requires work.

7. Comparison method. By using this method, it is intended to achieve a clear understanding of the essence of the knowledge and concepts given to the students on the topic. In the course of the lesson, to determine the similar and different characteristics of musical genres, to show the distinctive aspects of local styles, traditionalism, performance ways, as well as to identify by hearing and listening to march and dance music with songs, is done by comparison⁴.

8. Method of musical improvisation. In order for students to better understand the emotional content of the music, you can invite them to improvise the melody in the same mood (for the given text). The mood of your own melody, written in sad, funny, mysterious or heroic text, will help you fully perceive the music of the trail. It is also useful to sing melodies, themes (if they are available for children) from the works you have listened to. This will help you feel and remember the music better.

9. Method of musical movement. With the help of movements, it is easier for children to "get into the picture", to feel the music "with their whole body", to go deeper into its mood. Since there is little room for movement in the classroom, it can be done sitting or standing by the desk; you can invite individual groups to move through the music tables.

10. The methodology of musical education is also classified based on the main goals of musical education. Based on the relationship between styles and the main tasks of musical education, three methods are distinguished (E.B. Abdullin).

Critical thinking technology.

This technology consists in developing an analytical approach to any material in the student. This technology is not intended for memorizing material, but for formulating a problem and finding its solution⁵.

Conclusion:

In the process of musical education, listening to epic works, singing, teaching musical literacy and musical creativity are important tools for all-round development. The performance of the epic and the actions of the characters in it lead the child to maturity in all aspects. Through musical-didactic games, songs and tunes, which are learned rare examples of the epic genre, help to develop the musical ability of children and help the child to grow as a well-rounded mature person. Music tunes and songs develop human thinking and consciousness.

⁴ Ibragimov, B. (2023). Types And Importance Of Innovative Technologies In Education. Молодые ученые, 1(20), 96-98.

⁵ History of Uzbek literature. 1 roof of 5 roofs. from the earliest times to the second half of the 15th century. - T.: Science, 1978, 328 p

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